

Gross And Histological Studies on the Interdigital Sinus of Nellore Sheep

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out on six Nellore sheep and the samples were collected from local slaughter house. The interdigital sinus of sheep was located in the space between the two digits and its opening was present anteriorly just above the interdigital cleft. Morphologically it was “V” shaped and consisted of three parts: fundus, corpus and collum. The lumen of the gland was filled with a dense secretory material and wool fibers. Histologically the interdigital sinus consisted of three layers: epidermis, dermis and fibrous connective tissue capsule within outwards. In the body or corpus region epidermis was folded into the lumen and was lined by stratified squamous keratinized epithelium with desquamated cells of epithelium towards adluminal surface, whereas in the collum or neck region keratinization was more. The dermis was made of dense irregular connective tissue and it consisted of hair follicles, arrector pili muscles, sebaceous glands and apocrine sweat glands. Sebaceous glands were closer to the lumen in the corpus, whereas in the neck region large sebaceous glands and hair follicles were appeared close to the capsule. Sweat glands were appeared as compound tubular glands varied in size and shape in the corpus, however in neck region the sweat glands were few in number and smaller in size. Each sweat gland was surrounded by circularly arranged collagen fibers and myoepithelial cells. The sweat glands were lined by simple columnar to high cuboidal epithelium, whereas the excretory ducts were lined by bilayered cuboidal epithelium.

Key words: Nellore sheep, Interdigital sinus, Morphology, Histology

INTRODUCTION

In some ruminants, there is a unique anatomical structure termed interdigital sinus in between the digits. It has been mentioned as a foot skin organ (Raesfeld, 1978), interdigital sinus (Bavdek, 1981; Konig and Liebich, 2009; Aslan *et al.*, 2010), interdigital pouch (Konig and Liebich, 2009; Aslan *et al.*, 2010 and Dyce *et al.*, 2010) and also it is termed as interdigital gland (Janicki *et al.*, 2003; Demiraslan *et al.*, 2014). These interdigital sinuses are found in the limbs of sheep (Dyce *et al.*, 2010), deer (Wood, 2003; Reiter *et al.*, 2003), Japanese serow (Atoji *et al.*, 1988) and Asian elephant (Lamps *et al.*, 2001).

There are many native breeds of sheep in India. One of the main breed is Nellore sheep found in the northern parts of Andhra Pradesh state. The Nellore sheep breed is found in three colors-white (palla), white with black spots on face (Jodipi) and red-brown (Dora). The inter digital sinus is a specialized organ with sloughed surface cells combined with the secretion of their glands to form a pungent mixture, which is used for marking of the animals and

communication of reproductive information (Konig and Liebich, 2009). These sinuses are considered as scent glands produced odorous signals and pheromones that play important biological roles in the non-specific chemical communication, as active territorial demarcation and also in the expression of social behavior in sheep (Epple *et al.*, 1993; Parillo and Diverio, 2009). Moreover, Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) mentioned that the gland has fungicidal and bactericidal effects, and protects against ultra-violet radiation in sheep.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The twenty four specimens of inter digital sinuses of four feet (below the fetlock joint) of each from six Nellore sheep were collected carefully from the local slaughterhouses. After observing the gross morphology, the specimens were fixed in the 10% neutral buffered formalin immediately. The tissue pieces were processed for paraffin sections of 5 to 6 micron thickness and were subjected to Haematoxylin and Eosin method for general histomorphology, Van Gieson's stain for collagen fibers and PAS staining for carbohydrates (Luna, 1968).

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gross anatomy

Interdigital sinus of sheep was located in the space between the two digits and its opening was present anteriorly just above the interdigital cleft (Fig.1). Similar results were observed by Suzer *et al.*, (2015), Awaad *et al.*, (2015), Aslan (2009) and Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) in different sheep breeds. From its lateral view the interdigital sinus was “V” shaped (Fig.2). Whereas, Suzer *et al.*, (2015), Awaad *et al.*, (2015), Aslan (2009) observed that it appeared as pipe-like and Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) and Calislar (1971) mentioned as tobacco pipe shape in sheep. The interdigital sinus was differentiated into three parts: fundus, corpus and collum (Fig.3). Fundus was the most proximal and the “blind” part of the sinus, located at the level of distal end of the first phalanx. The corpus or body runs distally and posteriorly directed and formed a sharp bend at the level of middle of the second phalanx, then it narrowed and continued as collum. The collum or excretory duct was antero- proximally directed and opened dorsally above the interdigital cleft (Fig.2). The opening was rounded. Macroscopically, the sinus was closed from all sides, and the opening, which was relatively large in diameter, represented the only communication with the environment and the only possible “entrance” for pathogen microorganisms. Similar results were noted by Suzer *et al.*, (2015), Awaad *et al.*, (2015), Aslan (2009) in various sheep breeds. The lumen of the gland was filled with a dense secretory material and wool fibers. The lumen was wide in the corpus than in the collum which is in agreement with the observations of Aslan (2009) and Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) and Demiraslan *et al.*, (2014) in various sheep breeds.

Histology

Histologically the interdigital sinus consisted of three layers: epidermis, dermis and capsule within outwards (Fig.4) which are corroborated with the findings of Suzer *et al.*, (2015), Awaad *et al.*, (2015), Aslan (2009) and Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) in different sheep breeds. Epidermis was folded and thrown into the lumen. It was lined by stratified squamous keratinized epithelium and desquamated cells of epithelium towards adluminal surface (Fig.4). The dermis was made up of dense irregular connective tissue and it consisted of hair follicles, arrector pili muscles, sebaceous glands and apocrine sweat glands. Sebaceous glands were situated closer to the lumen. Sweat glands were appeared as compound tubular glands varied in size and shape. Each sweat gland was surrounded by circularly arranged collagen fibers and myoepithelial cells (Fig.4). The sweat glands were lined by simple columnar to high cuboidal epithelium, whereas the excretory ducts were lined by bilayered cuboidal epithelium (Fig.5). These results are in accordance with

the observations of Suzer *et al.*, (2015) and Aslan (2009) in sheep. The cells were highly eosinophilic and nuclei were euchromatic. The surface of the cells showed apocrine buds frequently. Acini of glands contained eosinophilic colloid, which was PAS positive (Fig.8). Similar findings were noted by Awaad *et al.*, (2015) in sheep. Hair follicles of different sizes were present in between the sebaceous and sweat glands. The fibrous capsule was present externally and made of dense connective tissue, contained parallel bundles of collagen fibers (Fig.7) and few elastic fibers. Fibrous capsule consisted of blood vessels, nerve fibers and also adipose tissue (Fig.5). Lumen of the interdigital sinus was filled with secretions of sebaceous and sweat glands, several wool fibers and desquamated epithelial cells. Abbasi *et al.*, (2009), Awaad *et al.*, (2015) and Suzer *et al.*, (2015) also reported the similar results in different breeds of sheep.

In the neck region of the interdigital sinus lumen was smaller as compared to corpus. The epidermis consisted of thin stratified keratinized squamous epithelium but keratinization was more. Many large sebaceous glands and hair follicles appeared close to the capsule within the dermis. The apocrine sweat glands appeared few in number and smaller in size in comparison with that observed in the body region (Fig.6). Lining epithelium was simple cuboidal type. Collagen bundles were less in number surrounded the acini in dermis when compared to body and these finding were in accordance with the Suzer *et al.* (2015), Awaad *et al.*, (2015), Aslan (2009) and Abbasi *et al.*, (2009) in different sheep breeds.

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Figure.1. Hoof of the sheep shows the opening of the interdigital sinus (Arrow).

Figure.2. Sagittal view of hoof of sheep showing Metacarpal (MC), 1st Phalanx (P1), 2nd Phalanx (P2), Interdigital sinus(IDS) and 3rd Phalanx(P3).

Figure.3. Interdigital sinus of sheep showing Corpus or Body(C) and Duct or Collum (D).

Figure. 4. Photomicrograph of body or corpus of Interdigital sinus showing Epidermis (E), Dermis (D), Capsule (C), Sebaceous Glands (SEG), Sweat Glands (SG), Hair Follicle (HF) and Secretion (S). H&E x 100

Figure. 5. Photomicrograph of body or corpus of Interdigital sinus showing Epithelium in sweat glands in dermis (arrows) and Blood vessels (BV), Adipose tissue (AT) in capsule. H&E x 400

Figure. 6. Photomicrograph of Duct or collum of Interdigital sinus showing Epidermis (E), Dermis (D), Capsule (C), Sebaceous Glands (SEG), Sweat Glands (SG) and Hair Follicle (HF). H&E x 100

Figure. 7. Photomicrograph of Interdigital sinus showing Collagen fibers (Arrow). Van Gieson's x 100

Figure. 8. Photomicrograph of Interdigital sinus showing strong PAS reaction in secretions and Apocrine sweat glands (Arrow) PAS x 40